

NEW DISEASE REPORT

First report of *Grapevine pararetrovirus* infecting grapevine in Greece

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In recent years, many viruses that infect grapevine (*Vitis vinifera*), have been identified in Greece (Katsarou *et al.*, 2023; Panailidou *et al.*, 2023). Further investigation to determine the presence of other known and unknown viruses in commercial vineyards has led to the detection of *Grapevine pararetrovirus* (GPRV). GPRV was discovered in 2022 in Russia (Republic of Dagestan) in samples showing symptoms of viral disease (Shvets *et al.*, 2022). GPRV is a pararetrovirus (family *Caulimoviridae*) whose genome is circular double-stranded DNA ranging from 7.2 to 8.5 Kb in size (Bhat *et al.*, 2016).

During the 2022 growing season, leaf samples from 55 plants were obtained from a commercial vineyard located in the prefecture of Messinia, a significant grapevine-growing region in Greece. Samples from each grower were pooled and sequenced by high-throughput sequencing (HTS) on an Illumina Sequencer, after having extracted total RNA using a Spectrum™ Plant Total RNA Kit (Sigma-Aldrich, USA). One pooled sample of leaves from four plants, collected in the municipality of Trifillia, had a total of 93,694,500 reads, with 35,320 mapping to the genome of GPRV (average depth 579.1, coverage 98%). To confirm infection by GPRV, each of the

four samples (prior to pooling) was tested by RT-PCR using the specific primers GPRV_2669F (5'-TAGGAGACTACTCTGACGACG-3') and GPRV_3086R (5'-ACTGGAAGCTTCTCTCTGGT-3') (Shvets *et al.*, 2022), which amplified a 418 nt fragment within ORF5 of the virus genome. PCR was conducted in 40 cycles with the following conditions: 95°C for 30 seconds, 54°C for 30 seconds and 72°C for 30 seconds. The expected DNA fragment was amplified from two of the four samples tested. The PCR products were sequenced bidirectionally by Sanger sequencing (Genewiz, Germany) and the sequence of the amplified fragments was 99% identical to the HTS contig. Two sequences were submitted to the GenBank (Accession Nos. PP584599 and PP584600). They had 91.4% nucleotide identity with GPRV isolate D1454w (OP886324.1) from Russia.

Leaf samples had a mild yellowing but as another virus (*Grapevine fleck virus*) and viroid (*Grapevine yellow speckle viroid-1*) were also detected, no conclusion can be made on possible symptoms. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first report of GPRV from Greece. This shows that the distribution of GPRV may be wider than previously thought and highlights the necessity for further surveillance to determine the true distribution.

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